

A NOTE ON THE ACTION OF THIONYL CHLORIDE ON 2:3-OXYNAPHTHOIC ACID.

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Meyers (*Monatsh*, 1905, 22, 791) on treating 2:3-oxynaphthoic acid with thionyl chloride at 50° obtained its acid chloride, m.p. 91-92°, whereas Kostanecki (*Ber.*, 1882, 25, 1642) distilled 2:3-oxynaphthoic acid with acetic anhydride and obtained γ -dinaphthoxanthone.

(I)

The dehydration product obtained in the present investigation has been assigned a structure (I) on the strength of molecular weight determination. On being boiled with sodium hydroxide solution, the ring is opened up and 2:3-oxynaphthoic acid is re-obtained.

Attempts have been made to obtain Kostanecki's compound for comparison purposes, but only acetyl derivative is obtained. Kostanecki's compound is described as dissolving in concentrated sulphuric acid forming brown solution with fluorescence, but the dehydration product, obtained in the present investigation, does not behave similarly.

Thus thionyl chloride is not found to introduce sulphur atom in this case, as it does in the case of 1:2-oxynaphthoic acid (Airan and Shah, *J. Bombay Univ.*, 1942, 10, 128) nor does it bring about either chlorination or acid-chloride formation, under the conditions described.

Thionyl chloride (30 c.c.) was added, 5 c.c. at a time, in about 20 minutes to 2:3-oxynaphthoic acid (5 g.) heated in an oil-bath at 110° in a distilling flask provided with a dropping funnel. The dry residue was extracted with chloroform, and ether was added to the chloroform solution when immediately a yellow solid separated. This was filtered, washed with ether, and treated with carbon tetrachloride in a Soxhlet apparatus to rid the compound of any free sulphur sticking to it, m.p. 240°, yield 50%. It gave no test for sulphur, hydroxyl group or carboxyl group. It is insoluble in dilute sodium hydroxide,

and has to be boiled with it in an evaporating dish for a fairly long time to dissolve it. From this solution a solid was obtained (by reprecipitation with hydrochloric acid), m.p. 214° (mixed m.p. with 2:3-oxynaphthoic acid). [Found: M. W. (freezing point in nitrobenzene), 155.3; Equiv., 189.2. $C_{11}H_8O_2$, requires M. W., 170; Equiv., 170].

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